

Research Topic: Beyond Push-Pull: Emotional Ambivalence and Digital Networks in Nigerian Teachers' Migration Intentions

Target participants: Nigerian Secondary School Teachers

Number of Participants: 10 (5 public and 5 private secondary school teachers)

Estimated Duration: 45–60 minutes

Moderator: Researcher

Recording: Audio (with consent)

PART A: Interview Guide – Introduction

Introduction (Moderator Script)

Thank you for agreeing to speak with me. My research is about understanding which secondary school teachers are thinking about leaving Nigeria to work abroad in this era of digital technology and why they do so. However, I would like you to share your experiences and views about your intentions to relocate abroad to teach. There are no right or wrong answers. I am interested in your honest views and personal stories as a teacher. Everything you share will be confidential. Please feel free to speak openly. May I record our conversation to ensure I capture your words accurately?

Do you still agree to participate and be recorded?

PART B: Interview Questions

Main Research Question

What are Nigerian secondary school teachers' perceptions, motivations, and experiences regarding international relocation intentions in the digital era?

Opening Question: Can you share a bit about your journey as a teacher? What subject and level do you teach, and how long have you been doing it?

Main Interview Question: As a teacher, what are your thoughts or feelings about the possibility of moving abroad to teach?

Probes

- Can you recall a specific moment or reason that made you consider this idea?
- How do you view the life of a Nigerian teacher who has moved abroad? What images or stories come to mind?
- What experiences in your teaching career have shaped your thoughts about relocating to teaching abroad?

- What are the biggest motivations or deterrents for you when it comes to moving to teaching abroad?
- In what ways have the internet and social media influenced your awareness or feelings about teaching opportunities in other countries?
- Was there a particular moment that sparked your interest in relocating abroad to teach?
- How do your colleagues impact your thoughts on the idea of teaching abroad?
- How tangible does the idea of relocating abroad to teach feel to you right now—does it seem very possible or just a distant thought?
- If you had to rank your reasons for considering relocation, what would be at the top? Is it for professional growth, personal safety, financial reasons, or something else entirely?

Others

- Is there anything about relocating that excites you but also makes you anxious?
- Is there anything else you would like to add that we have not covered?

Closing Script

Thank you very much for your time and honesty. Your insights are valuable to this research. If you have any questions after this interview, please feel free to contact me using the information on the participant information sheet. Have a good day.